

A randomization test and software to compare ecological communities

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Some typical assumptions made in many statistical tests include (1) random sampling of individuals from the population of interest, (2) equal population standard deviations or means for two groups tested, and (3) normal distributions for index values within groups (Manly 1997). In community analyses, however, data usually have taxa as indices and samples or communities as groups to be tested, and complex relations exist among different taxa. These assumptions are generally not met. Randomization is an effective method for tests of a hypothesis with community data and has been used in rice community studies (Zhang and Schoenly 1999a).

Suppose that there are s taxa in both community i and community j . Let x_{ki} be the number of individuals from taxon k in community i , $k = 1, 2, \dots, s$; $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. For communities i and j , $i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1$; $j > i$, calculate the Euclidean distance (de_{ij}), Manhattan distance (dm_{ij}), and difference coefficient (dc_{ij}) as follows:

$$de_{ij} = \sqrt{(\sum (x_{ki} - x_{kj})^2 / s)}$$

$$dm_{ij} = \sum |x_{ki} - x_{kj}| / s$$

$$dc_{ij} = 1 - \sum (x_{ki} x_{kj}) / \sqrt{(\sum x_{ki}^2 \sum x_{kj}^2)}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1; j > i$

where summation is over the taxa, $k = 1, 2, \dots, s$. The weighted standard Euclidean distance, weighted standard Manhattan distance, and weighted standard

difference coefficient can be calculated as

$$dwe_{ij} = \sqrt{(\sum w_k (xx_{ki} - xx_{kj})^2 / s)}$$

$$dwm_{ij} = \sum w_k |xx_{ki} - xx_{kj}| / s$$

$$dwc_{ij} = 1 - \sum (w_k xx_{ki} xx_{kj}) / \sqrt{(\sum w_k xx_{ki}^2 \sum w_k xx_{kj}^2)}$$

$i = 1, 2, \dots, n - 1; j > i$

where w_k is the weighting value for the k th taxon, $\sum w_k = 1$, and $xx_{ki} = (x_{ki} - \min x_{ii}) / (\max x_{ii} - \min x_{ii})$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, s$

where $\min x_{ii} = \min (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{is})$ and $\max x_{ii} = \max (x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{is})$.

The randomization test employed is based on the idea that, if no difference exists, then the distribution of individuals in communities i and j will be a result of allocating the mixed community values at random into two groups of a size equal to that of the original communities. The test involves comparing the observed difference between communities i and j with the distribution of differences found with random allocation (Manly 1997, Zhang and Schoenly 1999b). The threshold P value in the test can be defined as 0.01, etc. If the calculated P value is less than the threshold value, then communities i and j can be considered as being significantly different.

Of these distances, dc_{ij} and dwc_{ij} describe the dissimilarities of distribution of individuals with taxa between communities, while the other distances describe the overall difference for both taxa

richness and abundance. If the functional importance for each taxon is considered to be different, a weighting value can be given to each taxon and the weighted distance should be chosen. The latter situation is recommended for use in analyzing functional diversity.

Two versions of the software were written for the algorithm. A Windows™-based version can be run on Windows 95 and MS-DOS platform or later with a desktop resolution of 800*600 pixels or finer. An Internet-based version can be run on the HotJava™ browser with an HTML file (105 b) as the introducing program. The data file required by each of the two versions, as described by Zhang and Schoenly (1999b), is a space-delimited .txt file in which the first row consists of a numerical label for each community and subsequent rows contain the taxon ID number (if the weighted distance was chosen, then they contain the weighting value for that taxon), followed by the sampled number of individuals for that taxon in each community.

These algorithm and software were tested against observed data for rice communities (L.P. Lan, pers. commun. 1997); they performed well.

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Newspaper: a new attractant for golden apple snail management

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Rice farmers in the Philippines widely use synthetic commercial molluscicides against golden apple snail (GAS) *Pomacea canaliculata*, with little, if any, consideration of hazards to nontarget organisms and the environment. Other management options are seldom employed on a community basis for various reasons. Farmers report that manual hand-picking of GAS shells is back-breaking and herding of ducks after harvest and before planting produces an itch among farm workers. We studied several attractant materials, including newspaper, as potential tools to minimize human health hazards and inconvenience in managing GAS. Newspapers, not known to farmers as a GAS attractant, are easily biodegradable, readily available, and recyclable. In addition, they do not threaten plant biodiversity loss. We hope that this tool will further reduce the misuse of synthetic commercial molluscicides.

To determine the efficiency of materials that attract GAS, a series of tests was performed

from September 2000 to February 2001.

Test 1. Leaves of three plant species familiar to lowland farmers [banana (*Musa* sp.), taro (*Colocasia esculenta*), and papaya (*Carica papaya*)] and newspapers were tested as GAS attractants. Each of the four materials was sized 6 cm² for uniform coverage of field water and soil surface. Each treatment was replicated seven times in a randomized complete block design. GAS were introduced at 0700 h in the screenhouse at a density of 10 m⁻² microplot under no-choice conditions. The number of GAS attracted was recorded from 10 to 60 min, and finally at the end of 24 h.

Test 2. Materials for GAS attraction were the same as those used in trial 1, but were tested under free-choice conditions in a 2×5-m plot. Treatments were replicated four times and placed randomly in the middle of large plots. Ten GAS were released in each of the four corners of the plot. The test began at 0630 h. The number of GAS attached to the

test material at 30 min, 5 h, 10 h, 24 h, and 32 h was recorded. At the end of 32 h, the percent surface area of material consumed was also recorded.

Test 3. The same attractants were again used for trial 3, but the only difference was that fields were treated with 40–40–40 kg NPK ha⁻¹ before transplanting. The trial was replicated five times under free-choice conditions. Materials were placed at 1600 h and, at 0800 h the following morning, the number of GAS within a 1-m² circumference and those feeding on attractants was counted.

Test 4. The test was conducted at the Banaue rice terraces in Mountain Province, Philippines, where GAS is a new problem. Since papaya leaves are hard to find, trumpet flower leaves were used instead. Our past surveys indicated that the local people have been using trumpet flower leaves to attract GAS. Other attractants used were similar to those used in earlier trials. The attractants were placed at 0630 h in newly prepared fields.